

INDICATORS OF SURGICAL BOWEL DISEASES IN CHILDREN

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Among acute surgical diseases of the abdominal cavity, acquired intestinal obstruction ranks second in frequency, second only to acute appendicitis, at the same time, the number of deaths in it is greater than in other acute surgical diseases of the abdominal cavity combined. The frequency of intestinal obstruction in relation to acute surgical diseases of the abdominal cavity can reach 9.4%. Intestinal intussusception and adhesive intestinal obstruction are most common in children, much less often - obstruction on the basis of Meckel's diverticulum, inversions and nodules of the small and large intestine, strangulated internal hernias [1, 2].

The purpose of the study: To develop immunological indicators of complications of surgical bowel diseases in children.

Materials and methods of research. To develop informative indicators of complications of surgical bowel diseases in children, patients were divided into 3 groups:

Control group-1 consists of 30 healthy children;

Group-2 consisted of 31 sick children with intestinal obstruction (IO)

Group 3 consisted of 30 sick children with chronic constipation (CC).

All children underwent immunological blood tests: cytokines (TNF- α , IFN- α , IL-8, MCP-1 and vascular endothelial growth factor VEGF-A) were studied.

Results.

During the immunological assessment of blood parameters in patients, a statistically significant decrease in the level of INF α with CC was found to 10.7 ± 0.23 pg/ml compared to the control- 11.6 ± 0.22 pg/ml, which is explained by the chronization of the pathological process and the depletion of the body's defense mechanisms with the formation of a state of immunodeficiency.

In patients of the main group, the INF α was at the level of control values, which confirms the acute onset of IO.

To study the nature of inflammation in the intestine, IL-8 was studied in the blood serum of patients and healthy children. Its significant increase in patients of the main group was found to be 1.33 times, on average up to 48.7 ± 3.39 pg/ml compared to the control values - 36.8 ± 1.44 pg/ml. At the same time, in patients with IO, a tendency to decrease IL-8 to 32.6 ± 1.93 pg/ml was revealed, which confirms the importance of dysbiosis in constipation in children.

As a result of apoptosis and cell death, the intestines disintegrate and destructure, which is confirmed paraclinically by the level of TNF- α in the blood serum. In our studies, the greatest increase in its level was found in patients of the 3rd group (comparison) to 149.7 ± 1.29 pg/ml, and in the main group to 136.7 ± 10.89 pg/ml against the control- 58.4 ± 1.84 pg/ml ($p < 0.001$). The results obtained, obviously, prove the disintegration of tissue at the intestinal level in our studies by the formation of megacolons or other secondary changes in the intestinal tract in CC and IO in case of obstruction.

Taking into account the above facts, the assessment of the chemotaxis process in patients selected for the study showed an increase in the level of MCP-1 in patients of the main group by 1.3 times (366.7 ± 20.69 pg/ml), compared to the control- 279.8 ± 28.6 pg/ml, which confirms the presence of an acute inflammatory process and activation of macrophages. In patients of the comparative group, MSR-1 was reduced to 183.1 ± 25.17 pg/ml, which is 1.5 times lower than the control values. The obtained result indicates the chronization of the pathological process and a decrease in macrophage activity.

The study of the nature of inflammation and the activity of inflammatory markers made it possible to determine bacterial infection. Thus, in patients of the main group, there was a 7.25-fold increase in PCT (up to 2.9 ± 0.64 ng/ml) in relation to the control group -0.4 ± 0.44 ng/ml ($p < 0.05$) and 3.2-fold increase against the comparison group -0.9 ± 0.06 ng/ml ($p < 0.05$).

Thus, with IO, an increase of IL-8 by 1.33 times, TNF- α by 2.4 times, MCP-1 by 1.3 times, PCT by 7.25 times was found against the background of activation of chemotaxis with the participation of endothelial growth factor VEGF-A. As a result, a noticeable positive relationship was established between INF- α and CD8- $r=0.34$, between INF- α CD23 $-r=0.38$, between INF- α and IgA- $r=0.39$, between INF- α and PCT- $r=0.36$.

At the same time, PCT has a noticeable negative relationship with CD16- $r=-0.31$ and with CD8- $r=-0.31$ against the background of a noticeable positive relationship with IgG $-r=0.32$ and INF- α - $r=0.36$.

This leads to the conclusion that INF- α is a more informative indicator of the effectiveness of the immune response, and PCT is an indicator of the effectiveness of antibacterial therapy in surgical bowel diseases in children.

Conclusion.

A noticeable positive relationship was established between INF- α and CD8- $r=0.34$, between INF- α CD23 $-r=0.38$, between INF- α and IgA- $r=0.39$, between INF- α and PCT- $r=0.36$. At the same time, PCT has a noticeable negative

relationship with CD16- $r=-0.31$ and with CD8- $r=-0.31$ against the background of a noticeable positive relationship with IgG $-r=0.32$ and $\text{INF-}\alpha$ $r=0.36$. It was found that $\text{INF-}\alpha$ is a more informative indicator of the effectiveness of the immune response, and PCT is an indicator of the effectiveness of antibacterial therapy in surgical bowel diseases in children

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